

The role of self-esteem and self-control on smoking behavior man: case study among college students

Mujidin Mujidin¹, Husnul Khotimah Rustam², Muhammad Rizqyanto¹

¹Faculty of Psychology, Ahmad Dahlan University, Yogyakarta, Indonesia

²Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Institute of Technology and Science Muhammadiyah Sidrap, Sidenreng Rappang, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Smoke and a collection of components in cigarettes can cause very serious diseases. More precisely can disrupt health and its impact on individual health psychology. The purpose of this study is to explore how much the role of self-esteem and self-control of the smoking behavior of students in Yogyakarta. This study uses cross sectional studies with random sampling techniques. Respondents obtained were 75 students who were actively smoking cigarettes. The measuring instruments given include self-esteem scale, self-control scale and smoking behavior scale. The findings of this research explain that when students prioritize positive self-esteem then they tend to reduce or not smoke. In addition, self-control can limit the desire of students to reduce or stop smoking. Students who smoke at least do not do that in front of many people or avoid the crowd so as not to make other people tight or cough. There are still a number of other things that affect smoking behavior with cognitive, social, and cultural treatment. The nation's expectations and hopes that students would continue to be healthy, optimistic, and productive. Smoking research is very important to trace its cause so that it can help improve the health level of human life in the future.

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Corresponding Author:

Mujidin Mujidin
Ahmad Dahlan University, Faculty of Psychology
Jalan Kapas No. 9, Semaki Yogyakarta 55166
Email: mujidin.psy@uad.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Smoking was considered very dangerous by some parties because it had a prevalence of contributors to health problems, so it can be said that smoking was a complex problem [1], [2]. WHO predicted that there were more than 1.1 million smokers worldwide which were characterized by lower middle income communities [3]. The impact was a disturbance in the balance or a decrease in the immune system [4]. It should be known by all circles, from various literatures, validation and dissemination there was a health relationship including imbalance, decreased immune system and other health problems with smoking behavior [5]. Another health problem was that it triggers cancer and occurred more in developing countries than in developed countries. Approximately 70% of deaths related to the main cause was the habit of smoking all the time [6]. Even smoking behavior could cause death, falling into the use of illegal drugs, alcohol use, injuries while driving, and suicide [7].

Cardiovascular, lung and cancer diseases could be active in the human body through the active activation of smoking [8], [9]. That meant, smoking had the potential to damage the physical health of individuals, especially students. Smoking was described as a very open gateway to drug use among adolescents [10]. Sometimes, smoking made individuals unconscious so that they tried to commit social or ethical violations in society. According to the Shahab [11] the fact was that many adult smokers came from

smoking as teenagers on a continuous basis which is a significant health problem in the community. Although, many knew the negative impact of smoking on health, but until now there were still many people who consume it all the time.

There are consequences that must be accepted by students when they become smokers including disturbing cognitive and health aspects [12]. This is not just a written impact, but when students often smoke it becomes unfocused with lecture material. The cognitive is slightly disturbed and his health decreases such as continuous coughing, no appetite, stomach acid rises, and so forth. Another problem with students is the loss of career opportunities because many well-known institutions and companies force employees not to provide smoking facilities in the room. So, these conditions instruct students to stop smoking as soon as possible. This was a problem and a social disease in society. A strong intervention to prevent the spread of the negative effects of smoking needed to be enforced. Stauz [13] explain that self-will is one of the internal interventions that was very useful to reduce and stop the negative impact of smoking.

This self-control should be able to be awakened from awareness of the negative impact of cigarettes that can harm individuals. Therefore, healthy actions and habits were needed, such as always maintaining a healthy body and controlling oneself [14]. Self-control strengthens the determination and desire of individuals not to depend on smoking habits. Supposedly, self-control was inherent in all ages, from children to the elderly. Including young adults to maintain self-control by protecting their health from the dangers of smoking [15]. It was true what Villanti *et al.* said because it was also proven by Moffitt *et al.*, [16] that people with greater self-control would have better health, wealth, and many other dimensions of positive human development.

With positive developments, it would certainly bring changes in a person, for example from the point of view of self-esteem. Researchers suggested from the results of their research that there needs to be an important encouragement and motivation to encourage individual smoking behavior [17] so that self-esteem would increase. Positive self-esteem gains lead individuals to self-protection, improvement of their subjective health and well-being [18], [19]. By respecting yourself, you can certainly prevent individuals from being influenced by illegal drugs. Smoking behavior is often associated with negative behavior and unhealthy behavior. This research contributes to what makes it unhealthy and its impacts. This includes panic, morning sickness, bitter taste in the mouth, discomfort, and even loss of appetite. Previous research has not been able to answer other reasons for smoking behavior and its impacts. So, this research is very important to do and has a novelty, namely the cross-sectional method by linking positive psychological variables. In addition, researchers saw that many students smoked from the Faculty of Psychology class of 2018 to 2021, so this was assumed to be unique and not the same as other faculties.

Based on the background of the problem above, the researcher would like to be interested in further examining the relationship between self-esteem and self-control with smoking behavior in college students. Students were the pillars of the nation that should be able to stand strong, healthy, controlled and optimistic to face all the challenges ahead. That way, researchers wanted to connect the expectations and hopes of the nation to the importance of the students' future. In particular, self-esteem and self-control are still rarely studied by most researchers. Therefore, the researchers wanted to test: the what is the role of self-esteem and self-control with smoking behavior in psychology students at Ahmad Dahlan University

2. METHOD

2.1. Participants

The population in this study were male students from the 2018-2021 class of the Psychology Faculty, Ahmad Dahlan University. This research is supported by the ethics committee and permission letter from the campus with letter number F.4/698/H.1/VII/2022. The research subjects described the phenomenon that occurred and were found to be male students smoking cigarettes. From the large population, it was determined that the research subjects were 75 male students. From a population of 358 students at the Faculty of Psychology, 75 samples were obtained and 35 students were used as scale trials. This is supported by Alwi [20] those who mention that for descriptive methods, the sample used is at least 10% for a relatively large population and 20% for a relatively small sample. From the population recorded, the sample criteria are more than 10% and are considered to be representative of the population, especially those who use cigarettes. The data collection technique used cluster random sampling technique. Each class has a variety of offerings so that one class is obtained which contains trials and samples. This technique was considered quite good and effective to get research samples, especially smokers. Smokers lived mostly from the community and belong to both micro and macro groups. In addition, data collection in this study was carried out online because it was still in the pandemic period so it was not possible to take data offline. This research was assisted by fellow researchers in the process of spreading the scale of the research conducted at the Faculty of Psychology, Ahmad Dahlan University, male students of 2018 and 2019 who smoked. Data collection was

carried out from May 10, 2022 to June 3, 2022. The previously obtained sample was 85 people but there was a problem with the research instrument being incomplete so the researcher assessed that 10 respondents' answers were not included in the analysis so they were reduced. Samples that have been verified as many as 75 people. Respondents' answers were incomplete and some of the answer sheets were torn, making it a little difficult for researchers to find out clear answers.

$$x = \frac{\frac{1.96^2 x 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05}}{1 + \left(\frac{1.96^2 x 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05^2 x 358} \right)}$$

$$x = \frac{\frac{9.94 x 0.25}{0.05}}{1 + \left(\frac{1.96^2 x 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05^2 x 358} \right)}$$

$$\frac{\frac{0.96}{0.05}}{1 + \left(\frac{0.96}{0.895} \right)}$$

$$\frac{19}{1+21.229}$$

$$\frac{19}{1+22.229}$$

$$0,85$$

$$0.85 \times 100 = 85$$

2.2. Research instruments

There were 3 scales distributed, which had previously been tested, namely the scale of smoking behavior, self-esteem, and self-control. This research has an ethical letter with a number F.4/698/H.1/VII/2022. The smoking behavior scale had four aspects, namely the function of smoking in daily life according to Aritonang [21]. Then, the self-esteem scale includes four aspects, namely strength, significance, ability and virtue from the perspective of Coopersmith [22]. Then, the self-control scale had 3 aspects, namely behavioral control, cognitive control and decision control from Sarafino and Smith [23]. After the trial, it was concluded that the smoking behavior scale consisted of 20 items consisting of 6 favorable items and 14 unfavorable items. Then, the self-esteem scale had 20 items consisting of 10 favorable items and 10 unfavorable items. Meanwhile, the self-control scale had 25 items. The favorable items were 13 and the unfavorable items were 12. In this research, researchers used content validity which comes from professional judgment answers. Content validity is the extent to which the components in the form of a measuring instrument are truly relevant and form a picture of the construct that is in line with the measurement objective. Meanwhile, in this research ou reliability. The reliability test was carried out using the cronbach alpha method. By dividing the items in two or three parts so that each part contains the same number of items, with estimation using the internal consistency approach. In Table 1 as shown in conoth d below displays a scale that measures student smoking behavior

2.3. Data analysis technique

The three scales of this study were analyzed using the SPSS 16.0 application for windows. Data analyzed used SPSS yielded complete findings such as multiple regression test. Multiple regression test was seen from the value of the correlation coefficient R, the joint contribution of r and significant value. Then, move on to minor hypothesis testing. The first was to analyze univariately, namely to see the relationship between self-esteem and self-control with student smoking behavior. Furthermore, if you had found the results, then proceed to the bivariate test or partial test. In the partial test there were two reviews, namely the relationship between self-esteem and smoking behavior and the relationship between self-control and smoking behavior.

Table 1. The smoking behavior questionnaire

No	Aitem	SS	S	TS	STS
1.	Smoking can relieve my anger				
2.	I smoke more than 5 cigarettes a day				
3.	I can make friends while smoking in public places				
4.	Smoking in the morning makes me lose my appetite				
5.	Smoking can make me anxious				
6.	I spend less than 5 cigarettes a day				
7.	When I smoke in public places I am less able to interact with other people				
8.	I am not comfortable smoking at night				
9.	When in an air-conditioned room I will look for a smoking area when I want to smoke.				
10.	When I feel cold I will smoke				
11.	Smoking couldn't calm my anger				
12.	I smoke less cigarettes when I feel anxious.				
13.	I smoke next to non-smokers				
14.	Smoking in the morning increases my appetite				
15.	Smoking can cause stress				
16.	I don't spend a lot of money when I buy cigarettes				
17.	I prefer smoking in the room rather than outdoors				
18.	I will smoke less when the weather is cold				
19.	Smoking increases my fear				
20.	I smoke less when I'm with friends				

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this study were that the hypothesis test H_a was accepted. The acceptance started from descriptive data containing hypothetical scores and empirical scores. Table 2 describes descriptive data consisting of hypothetical and empirical values that aim to describe true and expected values.

Table 2. Research descriptive statistics

Variabel	Hypothetical Score				Empirical Score			
	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Smoking behavior	20	80	50	10	33	53	41,75	4,077
Self esteem	20	80	50	10	37	66	51,20	7,978
Self control	25	100	62.5	12.5	48	79	66.87	7.110

Note: Min=minimum, max=maximum, mean=mean, SD=standard deviation

First, the minimum score results are obtained based on multiplying the number of items with the lowest value from the weighting of the answer choices. The maximum score results are obtained based on the multiplication of the number of items with the highest value weighting the answer choices. The mean score results are obtained based on the maximum score with the minimum score and then the results are divided by two. The standard deviation score results are obtained based on the results of subtracting the maximum score from the minimum score and then dividing the results by six. After that, it is seen from the hypothetical mean and hypothetical standard deviation. Categorization norms can be seen in the Table 3, it describes the norms of scales and corresponding categories at low, medium and high levels

Table 3. Categorization of research scale norms

Norma	Categorization
$M-1.5 SD \leq X < M-0.5 SD$	Low
$M-0.5 SD \leq X < M+0.5 SD$	Middle
$M+0.5 SD \leq X < M+1.5 SD$	High

The data above became a reference for determining the categorization of subjects starting from low, medium and high. The researcher took a hypothetical score so that the smoking behavior variable was found to have a moderate category with a value of $F=53$, $\%=70.7$, and interval $37.7 < X < 45.7$. Followed by the high category of 20%, the value of $F=15$ and the interval $45.7 < X$. It can be concluded that in the smoking behavior scale, the most minor category was low while the moderate category dominated. Furthermore, from 75 research subjects there were 17 subjects (22.7%) who had a high category, while 45 subjects (60%) had a

medium category, and those who had a low category are 13 subjects (17.3%) which meant that the medium category dominated. self-esteem scale. The high category interval is $59.1 < X$. The interval for the medium category was $43.3 < X < 59.1$. Furthermore, the low category had an interval of $X < 43.3$. The same was true for the self-control variable. The high category interval was $71 < X$ with the value of $F=19$, and the percentage is 25.3%. Judging from the medium category, the value of $F=51$, the percentage was 68% and the interval was $59.8 < X < 71$. There was also a little treatment in the low category, namely 6.7% with the value of $F=5$ and the interval $X < 59.8$. We could learn that the maximum category was moderate, which was 51 people (68%). This was agreed by Fauzan [24] self-control was both classified as moderate. The similarity of Fauzan's research results strongly supported the results of this study.

Fund the statistical descriptive data, then continued to test the hypothesis. Based on the Table 4, the score in column R was 0.616 with $p=0.000$ ($p < 0.01$), $F=21.959$, so it can be concluded that the hypothesis was accepted. These results also showed that there was a relationship between self-esteem and self-control with smoking behavior in male students of the 2018-2021 class of the Faculty of Psychology, Ahmad Dahlan University. Agreement had begun to appear with the results of this study, especially from the results of research [25] that self-control was able to make individuals resist desires, and temptations of any form beyond self-control, including the temptation to smoke from friends and the surrounding environment. It should also be noted that the significant decreased in smoking behavior was assisted by increased self-esteem, similar to the results of research [26]. They conveyed feelings of high self-esteem can protect individuals against the desire to smoke. The hypothesis of this study is described in Table 4 and Table 5. Table 4 describes multiple linear regression results and Table 5 describes partial bivariate test results

Table 4. Multiple regression analysis test results

Variabel	Coefisen Correlation (R)	F	Sig (p)	Information
Self esteem and self control with smoking behavior	0.616	21,959	0.000	Very significant

Table 5. Partial bivariat test results

Variabel	Partial correlation (r)	t	Sig (p)	Information
Self esteem with smoking behavior	-0.292	-2,588	0.012	Hypothesis accepted
Self control with smoking behavior	-0.231	-2,019	0.047	Hypothesis accepted

The Table 5 showed the relationship between variable X1 and variable X2 to Y. X1 was self-esteem and smoking behavior. And X2 was self control with smoking behavior. There were values that appear such as partial correlation values (r), t values, and significant values. Based on the results of the analysis of the minor hypothesis above, it showed that the first minor hypothesis obtained a partial correlation coefficient (r)-0, 292 and a significance level (p) 0.012 ($p < 0.05$), it was concluded that there was a negative relationship between self-esteem and smoking behavior. in male students of the 2018-2021 class of the Faculty of Psychology, Ahmad Dahlan University, which meant that the higher the self-esteem, the lower the smoking behavior and vice versa, the lower the self-esteem, the higher the smoking behavior.

Then in the second minor hypothesis with a partial correlation (r)-0.231 with a significance level of 0.047 ($p < 0.05$), it was concluded that there was a negative relationship between self-control and smoking behavior in male students of 2018-2021 Faculty of Psychology, Ahmad University. Dahlan, which meant that the higher the self-control, the lower the smoking behavior and vice versa, the lower the self-control, the higher the smoking behavior. The effective contribution of self-control was obtained based on the formula $SE = \text{Score Beta} \times r$ (Zero Order) $\times 100\%$. In this study the results of the correlation coefficient (R) was equal to $(0.616) \times 100\% = 37.8\%$. While the rest ($100\% - 37.8\% = 62.2\%$). Was another factor beyond self-esteem and self-control that could affect smoking behavior.

4. DISCUSSION

Smoking behavior is a behavior that is not good to do because there are poisons in the cigarette butts. However, the findings of this study exclude smoking behavior with good self-esteem stimulus and high self-control. The presence of these two predictors makes students think positively and be kind to themselves. And this encourages individuals to think more about what the great dangers would be. Students display their self-esteem not by smoking so as to control their desires and change their goals to positive attitudes. Building a positive attitude towards the war against smoking was better, in line with the findings of [27]. They added that the highest positive attitude of smoking was being aware of the health hazards behind the negative

effects of smoking. Students consider smoking uncomfortable, making them nauseous and even disgusted with using cigarettes.

Individual efforts to continue smoking should not need to be continued. This suggestion came from the research results [28] that individuals felt the pleasure of smoking, boredom, habit, and stress. That meant smoking did not relieve one's boredom or stress. Students learn to self-evaluate and monitor themselves so that they are able to catch dangerous signals if they continue to smoke. So far, the effect of self-esteem on college students smoking is the power to be much better clearly reminded them. In addition, they feel much more significant than before. Students take part in several organizations on campus to focus their attention and direct their soft skills which are useful for the future. They are also wiser over time. There was no guarantee that smoking relieved stress and boredom so that self-control and self-esteem were needed. Individuals who had positive self-esteem tend not to think that other people's insults or innuendos brought them down. Stayed on track and saw the positive side of others. This was the key to living a happier and more grateful life. By reducing to eliminating smoking, individuals will be more meaningful in their lives more positively, willing to learn, fill time with positive activities to plan for the future better [29], [30].

Although the results of self-esteem in this study were significant, it was different from the results of the research of [31] Which explained that low individual self-esteem was shown by listening more to what friends said and engaged in romantic relationships such as adult scenes. The effect of self-esteem was slight in previous studies. [32] answered clearly that there was support, encouraging each other in any case, getting positive influence and positive thinking was able to release individuals from high self-esteem thereby affecting the intensity of student behavior. Individuals tend to accepted and respected themselves and did not need to get recognition from others in the sense that students have self-esteem and do not need recognition from others because they have values and guidelines for their own life without intervention or the desire to be someone else. Self-esteem was also correlated with social competence and made interpersonal relationships better. This statement was supported by [33] which stated that the influence of self-esteem could improve mood and respected so that individuals paid attention to their smoking habits.

Exactly, there were two factors associated with this research, namely self-esteem and self-control. The low self-esteem in this study was not the same as the results of this study which stated that the category was moderate. Slightly higher than previous studies. According to [34] that self-esteem was an evaluation made by an individual regarding matters relating to himself, which was expressed in the form of an attitude of agreeing or disagreeing and showing that the individual believed himself to be a capable, important, and important individual. and valuable. Supporting findings were also found in research that self-esteem influences smoking behavior in college students [35].

Individuals who felt that they deserved to be healthy tend to love themselves by avoiding things that could damage them from suffering cigarette. It meant that the more individuals felt in love with themselves, the higher the self-esteem that existed in the individual, the more valuable they felt, the more the individual stayed away from negative things that would arise on him, one of which was smoking. Based on the categorization that had been done on the self-esteem variable, it could be seen that 27.7% of the subjects had the high category, 64% of the subjects had the medium category, and 13.3% of the subjects had the low category. Self-esteem was associated with positive things, including the habit of reducing one cigarette at a time each day. According to research by [36] if smoking behavior was high, it was likely that his self-esteem was low. So, it was recommended to further increase self-esteem according to the results of this study, self-esteem was classified as moderate. The best was not low and slightly different from the low category.

Then, self-control was also influential in this study. However, if self-control was high as in the results of this study, it would reduce the individual's desire or intention to smoke. Self-control was also classified as moderate in this study, but this proved that there was a change in students because their smoking intensity was not high. On the other hand, the predictor that influences is self-control. Self-control keeps students on a path that conforms to norms, such as not smoking in front of many people or not endangering other people's lives. Students who control themselves also control their cigarette intake, such as considering how much they spend to buy cigarettes [37]. Purchasing cigarettes is also related to student decision making. Students prefer the right choice by not smoking and want to live healthier so they can focus on studying and organizing on campus. The strength of the results of this study was the that the effect of self-control such as knowledge, behavioral control and intention to smoke was significant on smoking behavior. Individual perceptions were strengthened by the control of their behavior and their intention to distance themselves from the negative dangers of smoking for health. Individuals were able to process unwanted information by interpreting, assessing, or relating events in a cognitive framework as a psychological adaptation or reducing pressure from the surrounding environment.

Students felt two components of smoking behavior, namely information gain and appraisal. With information that students trust, it could be determined that students had anticipated the dangers of smoking from the start. He did not join a group of heavy smokers. In addition, student assessment was trying to assess

and interpret a situation or event by paying attention to the positive aspects subjectively. For example, the pocket money increased by not buying cigarettes. Or set aside money to build a simple business so that you could be financially independent. That was from a financial perspective, then the other good news was that the culture of mutual respected and helped each other was strong. The mind became clearer and can solve problems with a cool head. Self-control was very important not only in smoking behavior. However, all activities that were negative or lead to evil must still apply self-control. Self-control was assumed to be a seat belt that protected student from all obstacles in the future, both from the health, social, economic, religious, and cultural aspects [38].

From the previous findings, the researcher also encountered several obstacles that became a weakness in this study. Moderate values in all categories were also a weakness because none of them was too influential. Portions were still moderate and not high. The results were influential but the correlation coefficient was still small. The fact that could be obtained was such as other external factors such as self-efficacy, positive affirmation, peer conformity, school perception, school satisfaction and other educational psychology variables that contribute to student smoking behavior. There might still be psychological and non-psychological factors that influence so that the results were not too high. In addition, aspects of data collection also needed to be considered. Data collection was carried out online during the COVID-19 pandemic, thus making data collection limitations. Dissemination using google forms or online was also feared to cause things beyond the control of the researcher, such as faking good on the subject's answers because the subject and the researcher did not meet in person. The small sample was also not reachable by the researcher. When participants fill in the answers, they might relate it to gender, especially to fellow men. The original participant gave the answer or even wanted to appear not smoking. For future research, researchers should create more challenging research designs such as experiments on cognitive, social and behavioral therapy in people who use cigarettes. Another method is to prepare FGDs to accommodate the aspirations of smokers and see gaps in the smoker's cycle. From this mini research, research formulations can be designed to be more interesting and produce many research findings. In addition, the sample selection also needs to be considered by including the female gender and a wider sample size

5. CONCLUSION

The smoking behavior model presented was a smoking behavior construct which was explored with the role of self-esteem and self-control in it. Self-control strengthens individuals not to be trapped in comfort, intimacy, harmony, or kinship that was interwoven within the scope of communion so that they were not affected by smoking behavior outside the limits. It was hoped that this research carried out could improve the study of psychology, especially in the clinical and health fields. For further researchers, it was expected to enrich references, especially regarding smoking behavior. It was recommended for further researchers to examine more deeply about smoking behavior not only for male students but also for both men and women, to complete the research. Suggestions for students were to avoid smoking behavior and also be able to reduce smoking behavior itself, this was because smoking can be harmful to the health of active smokers and passive smokers. Furthermore, the Ahmad Dahlan University Faculty of Psychology campus can help provide education about the dangers of smoking for health in order to be able to reduce the level of smoking.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Mujidin Mujidin A lecturer who focuses on the field of educational psychology, psychology student, student delays at Ahmad Dahlan University. Mujidin completed his S1 education at IKIP Yogyakarta. S2 at Universitas Gadjah Mada majoring in Psychology and S3 at Universitas Sains Malaysia majoring in Psychology. He was the head of the Master of Psychology study program, Universitas Ahmad Dahan. He has an interest in research on student limitations and student success in completing student academic and non-academic tasks. He can be contacted at email: Mujidin.psy@uad.ac.id.

Husnul Khotimah Rustam Husnul Khotimah Rustam taught at the Muhammadiyah Sidrap Institute of Health and Science Technology for several years. Husnul completed his S1 education at Makassar State University majoring in Psychology and S2 at Ahmad Dahlan University majoring in Psychology. Husnul has an interest in psychology and health. Psychological research includes motivation, self-efficacy, student involvement, and so on. Health research includes the fields of nursing, awareness and so on. She can be contacted at email: husnulkhotimahr6@gmail.com.

Muhammad Rizqyanto Rizqyanto completed his S1 majoring in Psychology at Ahmad Dahlan University. Continue to develop yourself and be very interested in clinical and educational research. Rizqyanto had attended a health psychology course so he was interested in the lifestyle of students and smoking behavior in Yogyakarta. Rizqyanto was once a course assistant at Ahmad Dahlan University. He can be contacted at email: mrizqyanto@gmail.com.